

SOCIAL SCIENCES

ANALYZE THE IMPACT OF CHINA'S BELT AND ROAD INITIATIVE ON THE EUROPEAN ECONOMY

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Abstract

The Belt and Road Initiative, a major international cooperation initiative put forward by China in 2013, aims to build an economic cooperation platform connecting Asia, Europe and Africa along the two main routes of the ancient Silk Road. These two routes are the "Silk Road Economic Belt" and the "21st Century Maritime Silk Road".

The goal of the Belt and Road Initiative is to promote policy communication, facility connectivity, trade facilitation, financial integration and people to people connectivity among countries along the Belt and Road, build a global connectivity partnership, and promote regional economic integration and global sustainable development through the principle of joint consultation, joint construction and sharing.

The main contents of the Belt and Road Initiative include the following aspects:

1. Build key projects such as cross-border economic cooperation zones and industrial parks to promote industrial investment cooperation.
2. Promote trade liberalization and facilitation, sign multilateral or bilateral agreements such as free trade agreements and investment agreements, and innovate trade methods.
3. Build a multi-level financing platform, set up financial institutions such as the the Silk Road Fund and the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank, and expand two-way investment scale.
4. Strengthen cultural exchanges and cooperation, carry out exchange projects in fields such as education, technology, culture, and tourism, and enhance people-to-people communication.

Keywords: Belt and Road, Development, Europe

1. Promotion of trade and investment between china and europe through initiatives

1.1 Promotion of Trade and Investment between China and Europe through the Initiative

By 2023, the "the Belt and Road" initiative will involve 151 countries and 32 international organizations, benefiting 60% of the world's population, accounting for 30% of global GDP and 75% of global energy reserves. Moreover, China's trade in goods with countries along the "the Belt and Road" has set a new record in 2022, reaching 13.8 trillion yuan. Since the launch of the initiative, China's "the Belt and Road" projects have totaled US \$962 billion, including US \$573 billion in construction contracts and US \$389 billion in non-financial investment. Overall, China has initiated approximately 200 transactions, involving over 3000 projects, established over 80 overseas economic and trade cooperation zones, and created over 420000 job opportunities for local people.

The "the Belt and Road" initiative is an open platform proposed by China to promote cooperation in Asia, Europe and Africa. It aims to achieve mutual benefit, win-win results and common development by strengthening five cooperation areas, including policy communication, facility connectivity, unimpeded trade, financial integration and people to people connectivity.

Provided impetus and opportunities for European economic growth, employment, competitiveness, and innovation [1].

China EU trade and investment are important contents and achievements of the "the Belt and Road" initiative. According to data from the Ministry of Commerce of China, in 2020, the bilateral trade volume between China and Europe reached 650.53 billion US dollars, a year-on-year increase of 5.3%, accounting for 16.4% of China's total foreign trade. At the end of 2020, China and Europe reached negotiations on a comprehensive investment agreement, creating new opportunities for both sides to deepen economic cooperation [2].

On the one hand, the Belt and Road Initiative has brought influence and contribution to European economic restructuring, sustainable development and social welfare by strengthening China EU cooperation in infrastructure, energy, green development, digital transformation, public health and other fields.

On the other hand, the Belt and Road Initiative has created conditions and platforms for the European economy to participate in the reform of the global governance system and build an open world economy by deepening the coordination and dialogue between China and Europe in policy communication, rule making, security and other aspects.

One Belt,One Road

- Silk Road Economic Belt
- - - - - Maritime Silk Road Initiative

1.2. The Benefits of China Europe Express on China Europe Trade Economy and Investment

China Railway Express (hereinafter referred to as CR express) refers to the container international railway intermodal train running between China and Europe as well as countries along the Belt and Road in accordance with the fixed train number, route, schedule and full journey operation time.

China Europe Express has laid out three routes in the West and Middle East: the western route passes through Alataw Pass (Khorgos) in central and western China, the central route passes through Erenhot in northern China, and the eastern route passes through Manzhouli (Suifen River) in coastal areas in southeast China. In March 2011, the first China Europe train departed from Chongqing to Duisburg, Germany, marking the beginning of the innovative development of China Europe trains. The opening of the China Europe train has strengthened commercial and trade ties with European countries, becoming the backbone of international logistics and land transportation.

In 2021, the 10th anniversary of the operation of the China Europe Express. In the past 10 years, China Europe Express has exceeded 40000 trains, with a total value of over 200 billion US dollars. It has opened 73 operating routes and reached over 160 cities in 22 European countries. In the past 10 years, the China Europe

Express has opened a new chapter in land transportation between Asia and Europe, forging a bridge and link for mutual benefit and win-win cooperation among countries along the route.

On December 18, 2022, the first China Europe train (Qilu) from the Shanghai Cooperation Demonstration Zone to Kopel, Slovenia will start.

China Europe Express is an international logistics brand under the "the Belt and Road" initiative and an important transportation link between China and Europe. The China Europe Express has advantages such as convenience, speed, security, stability, and a green economy, providing new logistics options for international trade between Asia and Europe, in addition to sea and air transportation. It promotes trade and investment facilitation for countries along the route, and builds a more open, inclusive, and inclusive "Express Economy"[3].

The China Europe train has reduced logistics costs and time. Compared to sea freight, the transportation time of the China Europe freight train has been shortened by more than two-thirds, and the freight cost has been saved by more than 80% compared to air freight. This makes the transportation of goods between China and Europe more efficient, economical, and reliable, improving the market competitiveness and confidence of both sides [4].

Data source: "China Europe Train Development Report (2021)"

The China Europe Express has expanded its trade varieties and markets. The China Europe freight train transports over 50000 types of goods, covering various fields such as mechanical and electrical products, automotive parts, clothing, shoes and hats, daily necessities, and food. The China Europe Railway also provides more business opportunities and choices for countries along the route, promoting the circulation of goods and consumer demand in the region.

The China Europe train has promoted the upgrading of the industrial chain and value chain. The China Europe Express is not only a logistics channel, but also an industrial chain and value chain. The countries along the route have achieved industrial complementarity and coordinated development through the China Europe train, improving their own industrial level and added value. For example, China and Germany have conducted deep cooperation in the field of automobile manufacturing, China and Poland have exchanged advantages in the field of agricultural product processing, and China and Belarus have conducted innovative cooperation in the field of dairy products.

1.3. The Contribution of China Europe Express to European Economic Growth

The China Europe Express has become the backbone mode of land transportation in international logistics due to its characteristics of short distance, fast speed, high safety, as well as its advantages of safety, speed, environmental protection, and minimal impact from the natural environment. At present, more than 70 operating lines have been opened, connecting more than 170 cities in over 20 European countries, increasing the vitality and potential of the European economy. The increasingly mature logistics organization of China EU scheduled trains, the increasingly active economic and trade exchanges of countries along the routes, and

the increasingly close cooperation between railway, port, customs and other departments among countries have all these favorable conditions, which play an important role for the railway to further play its role as the backbone of international logistics, and in the "the Belt and Road" strategy to transform the Silk Road from the original "trade road" to the "economic belt" with industry and population concentration.

The China Europe Express has provided more market opportunities and development space for European enterprises, injecting new impetus into European economic growth. According to data from the European Bureau of Statistics, in 2020, China surpassed the United States to become the EU's largest trading partner, with bilateral trade reaching 586.2 billion euros, a year-on-year increase of 5.3%.

The China Europe train has created employment and income in Europe. The China Europe Express has provided a large number of employment opportunities and income sources for European logistics, industry, commerce, and other fields, contributing to social stability and improving people's livelihoods in Europe. According to a research report by Roland Berger, a German consulting firm, the China Europe train creates approximately 11000 jobs in Germany every year, bringing about 1 billion euros in economic benefits.

The China Europe train has enhanced European competitiveness and innovation capabilities. The China Europe Express provides faster, more flexible, and more reliable logistics services for European companies, enhancing their competitive advantage in the international market. At the same time, the China Europe train has also promoted cooperation among countries along the route in areas such as green development, digital transformation, and public health, stimulating the innovation vitality and potential of both sides.

Randomly selecting six European countries, we can clearly see that GDP is showing a growth trend, and the data is sourced from the World Bank.

2. The belt and road initiative promotes china eu cooperation in various fields

2.1. In terms of green development

Green is the background of jointly building the "the Belt and Road". Green development is the direction of world development and the responsibility and mission of all countries in the world. In 2020, China announced to the world its goal of reaching carbon peak by 2030 and achieving carbon neutrality by 2060. In 2021, China released the "Action Plan for Carbon Peak before 2030". In 2019, The European Union announced the "European Green Association". Both China and Europe attach great importance to the construction of ecological civilization and the response to climate change, and regard green as the joint construction of the "the Belt and Road". The important principles and objectives of. The two sides have conducted extensive cooperation in areas such as clean energy, green infrastructure, environmental protection, and circular economy, making contributions to promoting global green and low-carbon transformation. For example, China and Europe have carried out multiple cooperation projects in the fields of renewable energy such as wind power and solar energy, such as the Pakistan Juba wind farm jointly constructed by China and Germany, and the Egypt Benban wind farm jointly constructed by China and France

Juba Wind Farm is one of the key energy projects under the framework of the China Pakistan Economic Corridor, and also the first cooperation project between China and Germany under the "the Belt and Road" initiative [6].

The project is jointly invested and constructed by China Power Construction International Corporation and Siemens Corporation in Germany, with a total installed capacity of 100 megawatts, consisting of 33 wind turbines with a single unit capacity of 3 megawatts [7].

The project is located in the southern province of Sindh, Pakistan, approximately 120 kilometers away from Karachi City. It has abundant wind energy resources and an average annual wind speed of 7.5 meters per second [8].

The project started construction in October 2017 and was officially connected to the grid for power generation in August 2019. It can transmit approximately 3 billion kilowatt hours of clean electricity annually to the Pakistan National Grid, meeting the electricity needs of approximately 1 million households and reducing approximately 900000 tons of carbon dioxide emissions [9].

This project is a successful example of cooperation between China and Germany in the field of new energy, providing useful experience and demonstration effects for promoting the construction of the China Pakistan Economic Corridor and China Germany energy cooperation.

2.2. In terms of digital transformation

In terms of digital transformation, both China and Europe are committed to promoting the development of the digital economy and digital governance innovation, and regard digitalization as an important content and means of jointly building the "the Belt and Road". The two sides have conducted in-depth cooperation in areas such as digital infrastructure, digital trade, and the Digital Silk Road, providing support for improving connectivity and service capabilities. For example, China and Europe have carried out multiple cooperation projects in cutting-edge technologies such as 5G, the Internet of Things, and artificial intelligence, such as the Rome 5G Smart City Demonstration Zone jointly constructed by China and Italy, and the Morocco 5G Smart Port jointly constructed by China and France [10].

The Rome 5G Smart City Demonstration Zone, jointly constructed by China and Italy, is a project aimed at utilizing 5G technology to improve urban management and service levels. The project was jointly promoted by Huawei China and TIM, an Italian telecommunications operator, and was officially launched in September 2022. It is planned to be completed by 2024 [11].

The goal of this project is to build 5G infrastructure and applications in some important areas of the city center of Rome, such as Vittorino Square, Venice Square, Spanish Square, and St. Peter's Basilica, including intelligent transportation, intelligent security, intelligent tourism, intelligent healthcare, etc [12, 13]. It can not only improve the quality of life of Roman citizens and the attractiveness of the city, but also strengthen cooperation and exchanges between China and Italy in the digital field, promoting economic development and innovation capabilities of both sides. [14, 15]

The first high-level dialogue in the digital field was held between China and the EU in September 2020, during which discussions were held on topics such as the digital economy, artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, and digital taxation. It was agreed to build a digital partnership between China and the EU. In 2015, a joint statement on 5G strategic cooperation was signed, establishing a dialogue mechanism on information technology, telecommunications, and informatization between China and Europe, and strengthening cooperation in 5G international standard formulation, technology research and development, and testing. Data flow.

In December 2020, the China Europe Comprehensive Investment Agreement was reached, which includes relevant rules for cross-border data flow and provides legal protection for cooperation between the two sides in the field of data.

In March 2021, a new round of China Europe joint research funding agreement and the fifth phase cooperation agreement of the China Europe Science and Technology Cooperation "Dragon Plan" were signed. In the future, both sides will accelerate the implementation of research and development projects, the establishment of cooperation mechanisms, and the exchange of scien-

tific and technological talents in fields such as agriculture, food and biotechnology, as well as climate change and biodiversity.

2.3. In terms of public health

Both China and Europe insist on taking people's health as the center, and regard public health as an important field and priority task of jointly building the "the Belt and Road". The two sides have conducted close cooperation in areas such as epidemic prevention and control, vaccine supply, and medical assistance, playing a positive role in maintaining global public health safety and human health and well-being. For example, China and Europe support and cooperate with each other in the fight against the COVID-19, jointly donate and purchase medical materials, jointly carry out scientific research and drug research and development, and jointly participate in global health governance and multilateral mechanisms.

3. Challenges and risks faced by the "the belt and road" initiative

3.1. Attitudes of different European countries towards China's the Belt and Road Initiative

European countries have different attitudes towards China's the Belt and Road Initiative. Some support or welcome it, some doubt or oppose it, and some are neutral or wait-and-see. These attitudes are influenced by factors such as the history, geography, politics, and economy of various countries, as well as the positions and pressures of Western countries such as the United States.

Support or welcome: Greece, Italy, Hungary and other countries are the first countries in Europe to participate in the Belt and Road cooperation. They believe that the initiative can bring them opportunities and interests in investment, trade, infrastructure and other aspects, as well as enhance their voice and influence within and outside the EU.

Suspicion or opposition: France, Germany, the United Kingdom and other countries are the largest economic and political forces in Europe. They are cautious or critical of the Belt and Road Initiative, fearing that the initiative will weaken the unity and cohesion of the EU, threaten European values and rule systems, and damage Europe's position and interests in global affairs. They were also influenced and urged by the United States and other western countries to require China to abide by the principles of transparency, fairness and sustainability in the Belt and Road cooperation.

Neutral or wait-and-see: Poland, the Czech Republic, Ukraine and other countries are important countries in central and eastern Europe. They are open or hesitant to the Belt and Road Initiative. They not only see the potential of the initiative in promoting regional development and connecting Asia and Europe, but also face pressure and restrictions from the European Union and the United States. They hope to maintain their own interests and sovereignty when participating in the Belt and Road cooperation, and balance their relations with China, Russia, the EU, the United States and other parties.

3.2. The positive and negative impacts of the Belt and Road Initiative on European economic development

Positive impact:

Promoted the growth of trade and investment between China and Europe. From 2013 to 2021, the total trade volume of goods between China and European countries along the Belt and Road has reached 4.2 trillion dollars, accounting for 36.2% of the total trade volume between China and countries along the Belt and Road in the same period; China's direct investment in European countries along the Belt and Road has reached 56 billion US dollars, accounting for 34.7% of China's total investment in countries along the Belt and Road in the same period.

We have improved the level of infrastructure connectivity between China and Europe. As an important part of the "the Belt and Road" initiative, China Europe Express has become an international transportation artery connecting China and Europe logistics. As of the end of January 2022, the cumulative number of China Europe freight trains has exceeded 50000, transporting over 4.55 million TEUs of goods with a value of \$240 billion, and reaching 200 cities in 24 European countries. In addition, China has also participated in the construction and operation of major projects such as the Greek port of Piraeus and the Hungarian Serbian railway.

It has enhanced political mutual trust and cultural exchange between China and Europe. China and the EU signed the 2025 Strategic Plan for China EU Comprehensive Strategic Partnership, and carried out multi field, multi-level and multi form cooperation dialogues under the framework of the "the Belt and Road". China has also signed "Certified Operators (AEOs)" mutual recognition agreements with 31 economies such as ASEAN and the European Union, simplifying customs procedures and inspection and quarantine requirements.

In addition, China has also carried out cultural exchanges with European countries along the route in areas such as education, technology, culture, tourism, etc., which has enhanced people-to-people communication.

Negative impact:

This has sparked concerns and resistance from some European countries and institutions regarding China's expansion of influence. Some European countries and institutions believe that the "the Belt and Road" initiative is a tool for China to promote its own values and interests in the world, which may weaken Europe's position and voice in global affairs, and even lead to internal division in Europe. Therefore, they have conducted strict scrutiny and restrictions on China's investments and projects in Europe, and even implemented sanctions and boycott measures.

Increased economic and trade friction and competitive pressure between China and Europe. With the promotion of the "the Belt and Road" initiative, China's competitiveness in the European market has continued to improve, but also faces more challenges and obstacles from European enterprises and governments. Some European countries and institutions accuse China of

lacking transparency and fairness in its investments and projects in Europe, suspected of dumping and subsidies, and damaging the interests of European enterprises and market order. In addition, there are also differences and controversies between China and Europe in terms of intellectual property protection, environmental standards, and labor rights.

In short, the "the Belt and Road" initiative has both advantages and disadvantages for European economic development. It requires China and the EU to strengthen communication and coordination, expand cooperation areas and space, properly handle differences and frictions, and achieve mutual benefit and win-win results.

3.3 Risks and Suggestions of the "the Belt and Road" Initiative in Europe

In 2013, China put forward the "the Belt and Road" initiative to promote policy communication, facilities connectivity, smooth trade, financial integration, and people to people connectivity among countries along the Belt and Road to achieve common development and prosperity. Europe is an important partner of the "the Belt and Road" and a beneficiary of the "the Belt and Road" construction. [16] In which areas does China need European technical support? China also needs European technical support in certain areas, such as chemical engineering. Europe has advanced technology and products in the field of chemical engineering, such as Kostron from Germany and Liquid Air from France. China still has a high demand for imported chemical raw materials, high-end chemical products, and chemical equipment, and needs to improve its independent innovation capabilities and international competitiveness. Software and simulation technology. Europe has rich experience and achievements in software and simulation technology, such as Dassault in France and SAP in Germany. China still has significant development space and potential for improvement in fields such as industrial software, simulation, and artificial intelligence, and needs to strengthen cooperation, exchange, and technology introduction with Europe.

Aviation equipment. Europe has leading technologies and brands in the field of aviation equipment, such as Airbus, UK RR, France Safran, etc. China still faces technological bottlenecks in aviation engines, aviation materials, and avionics, and needs to accelerate independent research and development to break through the "bottleneck" problem.

Industrial equipment. Europe has advantages and innovation in the field of industrial equipment, such as Achemir in Switzerland and ABB in Sweden. China still heavily relies on imports in fields such as CNC machine tools, high-end sensors, and intelligent manufacturing, and needs to improve its level of independent design and manufacturing.

In Europe, the joint construction of the "the Belt and Road" faces a complex situation of opportunities and risks. On the one hand, European countries hold an open and inclusive attitude towards the "the Belt and Road" initiative, believing that it is a platform conducive to promoting connectivity, mutual trust and cooperation, and promoting multilateralism [17].

European countries and China have extensive cooperation space and potential in areas such as infrastructure construction, energy resource development, and digital economy innovation [18]. The two sides can also strengthen coordination and cooperation on global issues such as tackling climate change and maintaining global public health security through the "the Belt and Road" initiative [19].

On the other hand, European countries also have some doubts and concerns about the "the Belt and Road" initiative, mainly involving transparency, standards, rules, debt sustainability and other aspects. European countries are also worried that the "the Belt and Road" initiative will affect European unity and stability and weaken the EU's influence and voice in international affairs. In addition, the United States has a negative attitude towards the "the Belt and Road" initiative, trying to obstruct and suppress China EU cooperation, bringing external pressure and interference to the cooperation between the two countries.

The Belt and Road also faces some risks and challenges in Europe, mainly including the following aspects:

1. Political risks. There are different political views and interest demands within Europe, and different attitudes and participation levels towards the "the Belt and Road" initiative. Some countries and regions are suspicious or hostile to China's influence and intentions, and believe that the "the Belt and Road" initiative is China's geopolitical strategy, which may undermine European unity and security. In addition, Europe is also under pressure and influence from the United States and other countries or regions, which may have a negative impact on the "the Belt and Road" initiative.

2. Economic risks. Europe has a relatively high level of economic development, intense market competition, and relatively complete and strict laws and regulations. This puts forward higher requirements and standards for project investment and operation under the "the Belt and Road" initiative. At the same time, due to the impact of the COVID-19, the European economy has been severely impacted, leading to the deterioration of some countries' fiscal deficits, debt levels, unemployment rates and other indicators, increasing the financing difficulty and default risk of projects under the "the Belt and Road" initiative.

3. Social risks. European society has a high degree of diversity, with differences in culture, religion, values, and other aspects. This may lead to communication barriers, lack of trust, misunderstanding and other problems, affecting the smooth implementation and social benefits of the project under the "the Belt and Road" initiative. In addition, there are also anti globalization, populism, protectionism and other thoughts and emotions in European society, which may resist or oppose the "the Belt and Road" initiative.

In response to the aforementioned risks and challenges, I believe suggestions can be made from the following aspects:

1. Strengthen political dialogue and communication. China and Europe should adhere to the principles of equality, respect, and mutual trust, strengthen politi-

cal dialogue and communication, enhance mutual understanding and trust, and eliminate misunderstandings and suspicions. At the same time, it is also necessary to actively communicate and coordinate with the United States and other countries or regions, clarify the true intentions and objectives of the "the Belt and Road" initiative, and eliminate external interference and obstacles.

2. Improve the quality and level of economic cooperation. China and Europe should fully leverage their respective strengths and potential, deepen the breadth and depth of economic cooperation, and improve the quality and level of cooperation projects. Specifically, cooperation in infrastructure, energy, digitization, green development and other fields can be strengthened, trade and investment facilitation can be promoted, stability and smoothness of industrial and supply chains can be promoted, and the challenges of epidemic impact and economic recovery can be jointly addressed.

3. Enhance social exchange and mutual learning. China and Europe should fully respect their differences in culture, religion, values, and other aspects, enhance social exchange and mutual learning, and promote mutual understanding among the people. Specifically, people to people and cultural exchanges in education, science and technology, culture, tourism, sports and other fields can be strengthened, people on both sides can improve their awareness and sense of friendship towards each other, and the social support and influence of the "the Belt and Road" initiative can be enhanced.

In short, the "the Belt and Road" initiative is an open and inclusive cooperation initiative put forward by China to promote global common development, and an important practical platform for building a community with a shared future for mankind. In Europe, the "the Belt and Road" initiative faces both important opportunities and some risks and challenges. Only by strengthening dialogue and communication, deepening practical cooperation, and enhancing people to people and cultural exchanges can we effectively address risks and challenges, promote the Belt and Road initiative to achieve more results in Europe, inject new impetus into the development of China EU relations, and contribute new solutions to global development. Therefore, to jointly build the "the Belt and Road", China and the EU need to strengthen communication and coordination, enhance mutual trust and understanding, seek common interests and the greatest common denominator of cooperation, and achieve mutual benefit and common development.

Conclusions

The world today is in a major upheaval that has not been seen in a century. Peace and development remain the themes of the times. A new round of technological revolution and industrial transformation is deepening, economic globalization is irreversible, and countries are increasingly interconnected and interdependent. Facing the future, the Belt and Road Initiative is standing at a new starting point of development. It requires all countries along the Belt and Road to work together, uphold the principle of joint consultation, joint construction and sharing, carry forward the

spirit of the Silk Road, jointly address risks and challenges, jointly consolidate, stabilize and improve the good development trend of China EU trains, promote the high-quality development of the "the Belt and Road", and work together to make greater contributions to building a community of shared future for mankind.

The economic trade and innovation cooperation between China and Europe has broad prospects and potential, but also faces some challenges and problems. In order to strengthen economic, trade, and innovation cooperation between China and Europe, I believe we can start from the following aspects:

1. Enhance mutual trust and understanding, eliminate misunderstandings and biases. Both China and Europe are important forces in technological innovation and face common global challenges. We need to strengthen communication and coordination, respect each other's development paths and interests, avoid politicizing or weaponizing technological innovation, and maintain a fair, open, and inclusive international technological innovation environment [20].

2. Expand cooperation areas and platforms, and improve the level and quality of cooperation. China and Europe have extensive cooperation space and complementary advantages in the fields of digital economy, green development, biomedicine, aerospace, etc. They can carry out joint research and development, technology transfer, talent cultivation, and other projects through the establishment of joint research centers, laboratories, bases, etc., to promote the sharing and application of scientific and technological achievements[21].

3. Strengthen intellectual property protection and rulemaking, and create a good atmosphere and conditions for cooperation. Both China and Europe attach great importance to intellectual property protection and have participated in the construction of multilateral intellectual property frameworks. Based on this, we can strengthen bilateral cooperation, promote mutual recognition and exchange of intellectual property, crack down on intellectual property infringement, and protect the legitimate rights and interests of innovative entities. At the same time, China and Europe can also strengthen rulemaking and standard coordination in emerging technology fields, form common technical norms and ethical norms, and lead the global governance of technological innovation [22].

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